

Assessing Muster Point Size in Relation to Staff and Guest Size During Emergency Evacuation in the Hotel Industry in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study investigated Muster Point Size concerning Staff and Guest size during emergency evacuation in Hotel Industries in Rivers State. The specific objectives were to examine the extent to which Muster Point Size vis-a-vis the total number of staff and guests in a hotel contributes to effective emergency management during an emergency evacuation. Using descriptive survey research design, quantitative and qualitative data were obtained through personal interviews and questionnaires to elicit information from the respondents. The study population consists of all 178 hotel personnel drawn from four hotels using a purposive sampling technique. The result indicated that while Hotel-1 has a 55.4% capacity which is grossly inadequate as required for the capacity in sizes or space designated as muster point, Hotel-2 has a 65.7% space capacity, Hotel-3 has 46.2%, and Hotel-4 with 54.1% capacity. Therefore, the muster point size within the study area will be inadequate to safely accommodate the population of staff and guests in the muster point in an emergency and during peak periods of emergency evacuation. The study also revealed a lack of adequate guest population data, inadequate size affecting headcounts, and limits medical personnel services access to persons with medical needs particularly due to overcrowding. Based on the findings on the inadequacies of these vital components for emergency evacuation management, the study recommends that for an optimum muster point size, hotel management should keep track of the numbers of guests, visitors, and third-party maintenance personnel to establish peak period population. Also, regular drills should be conducted to assess the adequacy of the muster point size.

Keywords: *Muster Point, Staff Size, Space, Emergency, Evacuation, Hotel Industry.*

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Introduction

Emergency management has long been identified as a necessity for the overall growth and development of the hotel industry, both in developed and developing societies. This growing recognition has led to the commitment of most hotel enterprises to strengthening their Emergency Management Systems (EMS). This is usually in terms of advanced safety and security arrangements to ensure increased reliance and confidence of hotel investors, employees, and guests, who form the core elements that foster industry development. Hotel Industries are generally faced with several emergency challenges that have the potential to lead to litigation and closure. When this occurs, it can be a major setback to societal socio-economic development and growth, more so when emergencies such as Fire, Explosion, Kidnapping, Terrorism, Murder, Death of guests, Medical Evacuation, Food poisoning, etc are involved. A well-deployed emergency management system becomes paramount to prevent or reduce the consequences of such emergencies.

In the previous decade, the hotel industry has played a prominent role in the development of Nigeria's economy with tourism capacity building, provision for employment, and cultural rebirth (Onugha, Ibem, & Aderonmu,2016; Obiora & Nwokorie,2018). It is regarded as one of the fastest-growing sectors in Nigeria's economy, equivalent to the communications sector (Bankole,2002; Onugha et al.,2016). This, therefore, implies that the conditions necessary for the overall sustainability of the business as a key player in Nigeria's economic growth, should not be overlooked. One of these conditions is to provide a muster point that is large enough to accommodate all persons within the industry during an emergency evacuation.

A muster point is a designated place or an area where all employees, guests, or visitors to the work site, or a large crowd can assemble in case of an emergency. The muster point ensures that everyone knows where to gather even in the panic of an emergency. The general assembly point enhances personnel safety as they can quickly be accounted for (Mishra, 2019). Instead of having people run off in all directions, a strategic meeting place allows the safety officer to take a roll call or attendance by using a list of all the people in the building. It also allows first Aid/Welfare deliveries to any vulnerable persons. Safety officers and members of the emergency response team are responsible for coordinating each muster point during an emergency until the incident is over. One of the most important factors in emergency management is the size of the muster point. According to OSHA (2022), accidents in the workplace often create panic, since it is an emergency, and the employee needs to get back his life. Hence, having a muster point where an accident victim runs to or where workers run to for safety in the event of an emergency is very important in Hotel industries.

The emergency management wisdom expressed by considering muster point size is key to emergency management processes. Though there are still other factors to consider such as muster point location and accessibility, the muster point size is a stronghold for emergency evacuation. The size must be adequate to accommodate all persons on the premises during the emergency. The assembly area is where the Emergency Response Team (ERT) will conduct the headcount of evacuees, and render basic first aid treatments where needed. Hence, the venue must be spacious enough to accommodate visitors, personnel, and members of the emergency response team, as well as the equipment for the emergency response team (Insurance Information Institute, 2023). Muster point size and staff/guest size during an emergency evacuation are central to managing the industry's Health, Safety, and Environment management system. Nobody expects an emergency or disaster, especially one that affects the Health and safety of employees, the environment of operation, and their business. emergencies and disasters can strike anyone, anytime and anywhere no matter the nature of business or job, the potential for disaster to occur is imminent hence, the need for proper emergency planning.

Emergency management action plans cover designated actions employers and employees must take to ensure employee safety and other emergencies. It is necessary or beneficial to include the management team and employees in the process of emergency management. Goals of protecting lives and property in the event of an emergency, commitment, and support from everyone are critical to the success of plans. A wide range and variety of potential emergencies that could occur in the workplace are considered in developing emergency management plan action. However, in emergencies, people are more likely to respond reliably when they are well trained and competent, take part in regular and realistic practice, and have agreed, recorded, and rehearsed plans, actions, and responsibilities, hence the importance of muster point cannot be pushed over. The Muster Point apart from being very central to the Health, Safety, and Environmental Management System, is a vital place of interest during an emergency and requires a deliberate effort to establish and manage it.

Nobody expects an emergency or disaster, especially one that affects the Health and safety of employees, the environment of operation, and their business. Emergencies and disasters can strike anyone, anytime and anywhere no matter the nature of business or job, the potential for disaster to occur is imminent hence, the need for a proper emergency plan. Emergency management action plans cover designated actions employers and employees must take to ensure employee safety and other emergencies. It is necessary or beneficial to include the management team and employees in the process of emergency management. Goals of protecting lives and property in the event of an emergency, commitment, and support from everyone are critical to the success of plans. A wide range and variety of potential emergencies that could occur in the workplace are considered in developing emergency management plan action.

However, in emergencies, people are more likely to respond reliably when they are well trained and competent, take part in regular and realistic practice, and have agreed, recorded, and rehearsed plans, actions, and responsibilities, hence the importance of muster point cannot be pushed over. The Muster Point is a vital place of interest during an emergency and requires a deliberate effort to establish it. Furthermore, to successfully determine the muster point size, the total number of staff, guests, and visitors should be properly tracked. Records of guests are domiciled at the reception. This can be found in the accommodation booking registers. Other visitors/guests should be tracked during social gatherings, conferences, and during maintenance activities. Regular tracking and data records of persons visiting the premises will aid in determining peak period population. The adequacy of the muster point size will therefore be assessed through this data acquisition process.

It is in the light of the foregoing that this study examined the Muster Point Size as it concerns the size of staff/ guests in the Hotel Industry in Rivers State. To achieve its aim, the specific objectives investigated the extent to which Muster Point Size contributes to effective emergency management, and the adequacy of the muster point size to the number or size of staff/guests in the event of an emergency evacuation in the Hotel Industry Rivers State. To this end, the study was guided by the following research questions such as - 'To what extent does muster point size contribute to effective emergency management in the Hotel industry in Rivers State?', and 'How adequate is the Muster Point size to the population of guests/staff during emergency evacuation in the Hotel industry?' On the scope of the study, the Content scope focused on muster point size and emergency evacuation of staff/guests in Hotels in Rivers State. Geographically, the study was conducted across 4 selected Hotels in the study area, with the unit of Analyses including the personnel working such as the safety Officer and junior, Middle, and Senior management staff as key informants or respondents for the study.

Overview of Muster Point Size, Emergency Evacuation, and Management in the Hotel Industry

Muster Point Size and Emergency Management in the Hotel Industry

A muster point is an allocated space in which all employees gather in the event of an emergency. It is considered the softest place on a site and all people inside the building should be aware of the muster point, being able to quickly assemble, should they need to evacuate the building for whatever reason. Once a head count has been carried out to ensure everybody from the building is present, people can be moved onwards to a further evacuation point (Creative Safety Supply, 2022). Mishra (2019) defined a muster point as a designated place or an area where all employees, guests, or visitors to the work site, or a large crowd can assemble in case of an emergency. The muster point ensures that everyone knows where to gather even in the panic of an emergency. Muster points allow supervisors or other designated personnel to perform a roll call and identify any missing employees who may still be on the work site after evacuation. This information can then be passed on to rescuers or emergency responders. Having all the employees gathered in one spot also allows medical first responders to quickly identify who might need treatment (for smoke inhalation following a fire outbreak, for instance) and to administer it promptly (Mishra, 2019).

According to Jay (2020), A muster point is the location that personnel evacuate to in the event of an emergency. Oladokun (2019) described a muster point as a safe, geographically defined place where people (i.e., the workforce and visitors) converge in an emergency to receive information and instruction, and for a head count before rescue operations are initiated if necessary. Ubongeh (2022) posited that a muster point is considered the safest place during an emergency, where every occupant on the job premises is expected to assemble for a head count before a rescue operation is initiated if necessary. Steve (2017) also described a muster point as a pre-determined area where all employees and visitors to an organization gather in the case of an emergency. According to Creason (2019), Muster points exist so that everyone knows where to assemble during an emergency. That way, they can be quickly accounted for. Instead of having people run off in all directions, a strategic meeting place allows the safety officer to quickly do a roll call or take attendance by using a list of all the people in the building, which is included in the emergency plan. With this fundamental insight into the meaning of muster point, muster point size is a significant component of the emergency management process.

The emergency management process consists of Emergency Evacuation planning which aims to reduce the effect of destruction caused by unexpected situations like accidents, fire, sabotage, spills, explosions, natural disasters, terrorist activities, and other emergencies. It shows the preventive actions, preparation to meet adverse situations, how to mitigate them, and how to have positive controls during that situation to save lives and reduce property damage (Safeopedia, 2019). Emergency evacuation planning is carried out by organizations, governments, families, and individuals. This planning is best conducted before emergencies occur. According to OSHA regulations, every workplace must have a formal evacuation plan that can be implemented in cases of fires or other disasters. Such a document should include specifications for Muster point with a significant focus on muster point size. alarm systems, detailed evacuation maps, emergency lighting, and a training plan that ensures that all employees are properly informed and trained, emergency drills should be carried out, allowing for evaluation of the effectiveness of the plan.

In an emergency evacuation plan, conditions precedent to carrying out an evacuation consist of when to shelter in place rather than evacuate, a clear chain of command, specific emergency evacuation plan procedures, specific evacuation procedures for high-rise buildings, procedures for assisting visitors, guests and employees to evacuate, designation of who will remain after the evacuation alarm to shut down critical operations or perform other duties, the way to account for

all visitors and employees after an evacuation, special equipment for emergency evacuation plan and appropriate respirators (Ashford & Foster, 2023).

Muster Point Size and the Population of Guests and Staff during Emergency Evacuation in the Hotel Industry

Emergency evacuation is an immediate egress or escape of people away from an area that contains an imminent threat, an ongoing threat, or a hazard to lives or property. This is achieved with a carefully deployed evacuation plan. The sequence of an evacuation can be divided into the following phases: detection, decision, alarm, reaction, movement to an area of refuge or an assembly station, and transportation (Ronchi & Nilsson, 2013). The area of refuge is the muster point, hence when choosing the muster point, the primary objective should be to find a safe area that can be reached easily and quickly. The following factors should be considered: the area should not have any features that could put workers at additional risk. A spot that might flood during a heavy rainstorm is not suitable for a muster point. Same with one that can only be accessed by crossing a high-traffic road. Avoid proximity to power lines or trees as well, since these can be knocked over by heavy winds. The muster point should be at a distance of at least one-and-a-half times the height of the tallest building in the facility. This will prevent fire, fumes, or flying debris from reaching the muster point. All workers must be able to make their way to the muster point with ease. If possible, avoid a location that can only be reached by walking uphill, taking stairs, or climbing over a barrier or other obstacle. Since everyone on the worksite must gather at the muster point, it must be large enough to accommodate everyone. Size is of great importance in the selection of a major point (Mishra, 2019)

Muster point size is of great significance while moving to the place of refuge and while examining employees' evacuation, it forms a core of the evacuation plan for a successful emergency management system. Buzinkay (2022), posited that while choosing a muster point, select one that is large enough from where to evacuate the entire workforce, a location that can safely accommodate all people on board, including visitors, guests, employees, and contractors. Mishra (2019) posited that, since everyone on the worksite must gather at the muster point, it must be large enough to accommodate everyone and for larger facilities, it is advisable to have multiple muster points at strategic locations to prevent crowding, and confusion, and reduce evacuation time.

Methods and Materials

The study employed the descriptive survey research design by which both quantitative and qualitative methods were used to obtain data through personal interviews and the administration of copies of questionnaires to elicit information from the respondents. This was with particular focus on the extent to which existing Muster Points locations, size capacity and evacuation strategies/management of both the staff and guests at the hotels selected for study conforms to (or contravene) emergency management requirements and guidelines for hotel industry muster point. The study which was carried out in Rivers State, Nigeria adopted the purposive sampling method due to the size of the population. By this, the total number of staff in the selected four(4) hotels, which is 186 formed the study sample and respondents, as well as the number of copies of questionnaires served, retrieved, and analyzed for the study. Analysis of results was done using descriptive statistics, frequency tables, and percentages based on information derived from the questionnaires and the interviews of the Safety Officers in each of the selected hotels.

Results and Analysis

Table 1. Staff/Guests Size Vs Muster Point Capacity in the Study Area

S/n	Items	Maximum Capacity (Peak period)	Muster Point Capacity
1	Hotel 1	264	120
2	Hotel 2	335	200
3	Hotel 3	260	120
4	Hotel 4	222	120
	Total	1,081	560

Source: Research Data 2023, (Microsoft Excel output version 2010)

Figure 1. Staff and Guests Size Vs Muster Point Capacity in the Sampled Hotels

Source: Research Data, 2023 (Microsoft Excel Output Version 2010)

From Figure 1, it is obvious that the staff and guest size at the peak period is greater than the Muster Point capacity during emergency evacuation. Staff & Guest Sizes in Hotel 1 is 264 against 120 person capacity of the muster point, Staff & Guest Size in Hotel 2 is 335 against 200 person capacity of the muster point, Hotel 3 will accommodate 260 persons including staff and guests, while the muster point capacity is 120 and finally, Hotel 4 will accommodate 222 persons at peak period with available muster point capacity stood at 120 persons. This is a case of inadequate capacity of the muster point, which will create a high risk during emergency evacuation.

Table 2. Questionnaire Analysis of the Importance of Muster Point Size Concerning Staff and Guest Size in the Event of Emergency Evacuation

Muster Point Size Services		Yes	No	% Yes	% No
1	Is the muster point adequate for personnel assembly during an emergency	9	169	5.06	94.94
2	Is the muster point large enough to accommodate the entire workforce and guests during an emergency	6	172	3.37	96.63
3	Can a headcount be conducted quickly to ensure everyone has been safely evacuated	82	96	46.07	53.93
4	Is there enough space to attend to basic first aid needs?	55	123	30.9	69.1
5	Will people be well out of the way of emergency services equipment and personnel so they can do their job?	51	127	28.65	71.35

Source: Field Survey Data, 2023

Table 2 illustrates the response rates, frequency, and percentage response for Muster Point Size characteristics measured on a 5-item instrument and scaled on a dichotomous scale.

94.94% of the population agreed that the muster point size is not adequate for personnel and guest assembly during an emergency. 96.63% of the population agreed that the muster point is not large enough to accommodate the entire workforce and guests during an emergency. 53.93% agreed that a headcount cannot be conducted quickly to ensure everyone has been safely evacuated. 69.10% of the population agreed that there is not enough space to attend to basic first aid needs during an emergency. 71.35% of the population agreed that there is not much room for emergency service and personnel to have access to perform their job role at the muster point during an emergency.

Discussion of Findings

One of the major qualities of a good muster point as earlier mentioned, is that the place designated for a workplace's muster points is not only safe but large enough to safely accommodate your entire workforce, that is, all personnel, plus contractors and visitors. This study on the Hotel industry implies a place sizeable enough to accommodate all staff and guests in the event of an emergency. However, the findings of the study showed that all the four hotels sampled do have adequate space in their muster point to accommodate all their staff and guests in case of an emergency, and therefore did not meet the muster point size requirement as earlier enunciated by Brad (2019) and Safeopedia (2019). For instance, in Hotel 1, the muster point capacity available is 120 persons compared to the total number of staff and guests combined which is 264 persons at the time of survey. This implies a 55.4% capacity which is grossly inadequate as required. In the same vein, the other sampled hotels lacked adequate capacity in sizes or spaces designated as muster points. While Hotel 2 for instance has a 65.7% space capacity, Hotel 3 has 46.2%, and Hotel 4 with 54.1% capacity.

The implication of this is that adequate space was not designated as a muster point in all 4 hotels, which means that there is a high risk of a stampede in the event of an emergency, people avoiding the place to avoid overcrowding of the muster point which raises another safety concern on its own. To meet the safety requirements in line with the global best practices, it will be ideal to distribute muster points around the perimeter of the hotels. This could help to ensure that muster points are not overcrowded, while also helping not only to ease the execution and coordination of an evacuation plan, but keep evacuation times low from all locations, most especially when designing an evacuation plan for relatively large hotels.

It is also observed that in all the hotels sampled for this study, the muster point size was inadequate at the peak period. This is a drawback for rescue services in the face of emergency in the Hotel Industry. The study therefore further reinforces the importance of appropriate space and muster point size in keeping to safety requirements for seamless evacuation of both staff and guests in the hotels if a disaster strikes. In summary, for emergency management to be effective, there must be in existence a safe refuge large enough to accommodate vulnerable workers and large enough to avoid overcrowding, while workers wait for further instruction to either evacuate the premises or return to work and thus, recommend efficient measures that could minimize the risk of vulnerable Hotel workers, Guest and Visitors in the face of an emergency.

Table 2 illustrates the response rates, frequency, and percentage response for Muster Point Size characteristics measured on a 5-item instrument and scaled on a dichotomous scale. The result showed that 94.94% of the respondents agreed that the muster point size is not adequate for personnel and guests to assemble during an emergency. This has brought about the need to have more than one muster point designated to serve a large workplace facility such as a very big hotel, to make them quickly accessible from various emergency exits of the building during an emergency

Again, while 53.9% agreed that a headcount cannot be conducted quickly to ensure everyone has been safely evacuated, 69.1% of the respondent population agreed that there is not enough space to attend to basic first aid needs during an emergency. These results show that overcrowding is inevitable and hence executing emergency evacuation protocols such as first calming down the victims, carrying out a headcount, applying first aid, etc before the final evacuation to safer grounds will make it difficult to achieve an earlier stressed in the works of Terry(2019) and Jay (2020).

One of the main aims of a muster point is to be able to carry out a head count as quickly as possible following an incident where everybody needs to be able to reach the muster point independently. For this reason, an accessible muster point is essential to ensure evacuees can get to the location, especially for rapid emergency mustering. (Andrews, 2022 & Jay, 2022). In this study, however, 71.35% of the respondents agreed that there is not much room for emergency service and personnel to have access to perform their job role at the muster point during an emergency. Again, this implies that the hotels studied here fail to meet this important condition of accessibility as claimed by the respondents. In all, especially in the event of an emergency, hotel muster points need to be accessible to everyone—including contractors, guests in the hotel, unplanned visitors, as well as those responsible for carrying out evacuation from the muster points (evacuees) when an emergency strikes.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined muster point size concerning staff and guest size in the Hotel industry during emergency evacuation. The study established that muster point size must, be of adequate size to avoid overcrowding, enhance medical caregivers to maneuver and render medical services where needed, and provide enough room for a seamless head count. The study revealed that for emergency management to be effective, there must be in existence a safe refuge large enough to accommodate vulnerable persons in the premises and avoid overcrowding, while workers wait for further instruction to either evacuate the premises or return to work.

The study thus recommends that to determine the size of the muster point, Hotel management should keep track of daily customers and visitor population to establish the population variation and have working data for peak periods. This will include the total number of staff, guests, visitors, and contractors/maintenance team as well as evacuees. There is also the need to review or upgrade Muster Point size by the population estimates from the daily population tracker, most especially for some large events hosted in these hotels from time to time.

Since performing a headcount, or roll call by which safety officers know that everyone has evacuated safely, the adoption of a digital mustering headcount is recommended, especially where the manual headcounts which require a designated person to perform them at each muster point are not feasible. The whole intention is for evacuation and safety officers to be able to confirm that each person is safe or communicate any missing persons at the time the headcount is being conducted.

Lastly, regular emergency drills to ascertain the adequacy of Muster point size and response pattern of persons at the Hotel should be conducted. This exercise will help to measure the indices of muster point overcrowding, medical services, and headcount activities to minimize the risk of vulnerable Hotel workers, Guests, and Visitors in the face of an emergency.

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